

Stylistic Characteristics of Phraseological Units with Numeric Components

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Abstract: This study provides a multidimensional analysis of the structural and semantic peculiarities of phraseological units to identify the general, the similar, and the national-specific, which are different in terms of phraseological figurativeness. Most of the magical images and symbols became the basis of the symbolism of the numerals, which became part of the phraseological units. The article focuses on problems such as the implementation of the concept “number” in Russian phraseological units with a numerical component, and it also considers the frequency of using numerical components in phraseological units of the Russian language.

Anahtar Sözcükler: Sayısal Bileşenli Deyimsel Birimlerin Üslup Özellikleri

Dilbilimsel farklılaşma,
deyim birim,
üslup,
değişibilim

Özet: Bu çalışma, deyimsel mecazilik açısından farklı olan genel, benzer ve ülkeye özgü olanı belirlemek için deyim birimlerinin yapısal ve anlamsal özelliklerinin çok boyutlu bir analizini sunmaktadır. Büyülü görüntülerin ve sembollerin çoğu, ifade birimlerinin bir parçası haline gelen sayıların sembolizminin temeli haline geldi. Makale, “sayı” kavramının Rusça deyim birimlerinde sayısal bileşenle uygulanması gibi sorunlara odaklanmakta ve aynı zamanda Rus dilinin deyim birimlerinde sayısal bileşenlerin kullanılma sıklığını da ele almaktadır.

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1. Introduction

The systematic differentiation of phraseological units within the framework of phraseology stands as a paramount pursuit pivotal to advancing linguistic sciences. This need for further exploration becomes evident in “style”, which encapsulates identifying usage patterns in speech and writing (Arikan, 2015), encompassing lexical-phraseological, syntactic, morphological, and phonetic systems by individuals or groups unified by shared interests, education, and communication specifics (Solodub & Albrecht, 2002). While communication serves as the fundamental function of language, its manifestation can assume more specialized forms: verbal communication involving information exchange or dialogue, the delivery of messages in oral or written formats, and the emotional or aesthetic impact on listeners or readers during information transmission (Ismajli & Krasniqi, 2022; Matabane & Machaba, 2023; Tamba & Iancu, 2023). These varied forms of speech activity delineate two functional styles in modern Russian literary language: colloquial and bookish.

The distinction in stylistic affiliation and expressive nuances among phraseological units arises from the unique linguistic tools and techniques embedded within each language style. Speakers draw from the reservoir of national linguistic resources to articulate specific content, thereby attributing certain phraseological units with greater prominence within distinct stylistic domains. Examining Russian phraseological material incorporating numerical components substantiates Molotkov’s (1977) assertion that “phraseological units primarily stem from colloquial speech”. Indeed, within the studied corpus, colloquial phraseological units featuring numerical elements overwhelmingly dominate: from idiomatic expressions like “the first person you meet” denoting any individual, to phrases such as “from the first nail” signifying the inception of something, or idioms like “at least with one little eye” conveying a fleeting or cursory glance. These examples underscore the prevalence of conversational phraseological units within the material under scrutiny, underscoring their significance within colloquial discourse (Hockett, 1978).

The intricate tapestry of language is interwoven with colorful expressions that breathe life into communication, providing vivid imagery and succinct conveyance of complex ideas. Among these linguistic treasures, phraseological units stand as pillars, encapsulating cultural nuances, historical contexts, and stylistic variations (Dudareva *et al.*, 2017; Gabidullina *et al.*, 2020). Within this rich tapestry, a subset of phraseological units emerges—those infused with numeric components—endowing language with a unique cadence and precision. In this exploration, we embark on a journey to uncover the stylistic characteristics embedded within these fascinating linguistic constructs. Phraseological units, often known as idioms, proverbs, or fixed expressions, are integral components of language that transcend mere word combinations. They encapsulate shared cultural experiences, historical contexts, and societal values, acting as vessels carrying a language community’s collective wisdom and identity (Stepanova & Lutskovskaia, 2019; Yudina *et al.*, 2020). When integrated into these units, numeric components add a distinct dimension, lending precision, emphasis, or figurative weight to the expression. At the intersection of linguistics and cultural heritage, the study of phraseological units with numeric components unveils a treasure trove of linguistic nuances and stylistic peculiarities. These units, enriched with numerical elements, encompass diverse expressions, ranging from idiomatic phrases like “at the eleventh hour” to proverbs such as “two heads are better than one.” They permeate various aspects of language, from everyday conversations to literary works, showcasing the depth and versatility of human expression. Understanding the stylistic characteristics of phraseological units with numeric components requires an exploration of their structural, semantic, and pragmatic dimensions. Structurally,

these units often follow distinct patterns, with numbers serving as integral components, cardinal or ordinal, specific or generic.

Semantically, including numerical elements, endows these units with metaphorical, idiomatic, or proverbial meanings, often transcending literal interpretations. Pragmatically, their usage manifests in different communicative contexts, carrying connotations of precision, emphasis, or cultural significance. Moreover, the stylistic features of phraseological units with numeric components exhibit intriguing variations across languages and cultures. The idiosyncrasies of these units reflect the unique historical, social, and linguistic landscapes of their origins. For instance, while some languages heavily incorporate numerical components in idiomatic expressions, others might use them sparingly, highlighting the diverse ways languages harness numerical symbolism within their phraseological repertoire. This comprehensive examination delves into the labyrinthine realm of phraseology, scrutinizing the intricate interplay between numeric elements and linguistic expression. Through this exploration, we aim to unravel the underlying stylistic characteristics, shedding light on the nuances and significance of phraseological units enriched with numerical components. Join us in this captivating expedition as we decode the linguistic tapestry, revealing the artistry and depth embedded within these fascinating expressions.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Phraseological Units Selection

The investigated materials consist of diverse Russian phraseological units incorporating numerical components. These were culled from varied sources such as literary works, folklore, religious texts, colloquial conversations, and vernacular expressions.

2.1.1. Classification of phraseological units

The collected phraseological units were classified into distinct stylistic categories: bookish, colloquial, and inter-style. Bookish phraseological units encompass those sourced from literary texts, biblical legends, and established cultural or mythological contexts. Colloquial phraseological units were sourced from everyday conversations, reflecting a more casual or informal language style. As per Shansky's classification, inter-style phraseological units are neutral expressions devoid of expressive connotations, commonly employed across different stylistic domains (Shansky,1985).

2.1.2. Interpretive analysis

The research methodology involves interpretive analysis focusing on evaluating the stylistic, evaluative, and expressive attributes of phraseological units. These attributes were identified and classified based on linguistic and stylistic characteristics, considering the impact of usage contexts and cultural connotations.

2.2. Framework for Stylistic Differentiation

The study draws upon theoretical frameworks proposed by A.B. Kunin and other linguists. Kunin's foundational concepts in phraseological stylistics, particularly emphasizing the normative and occasional stylistic properties of phraseological units, serve as a guiding principle. This includes classification based on normative stylistic functions and the typology of expressive phraseological means when integrated into textual contexts (Kunin,1969).

2.2.1. *Assessment of expressiveness*

Expressiveness, a crucial characteristic, is evaluated as per Lukyanova's and other scholars' definitions. This analysis aspect aims to gauge how phraseological units convey vividness, intensity, and qualitative attributes, enhancing the semantic content and perceptual impact within communication (Lukyanova, 1989).

2.2.2. *Emphasis on evaluative-expressive features*

Special attention is given to exploring the evaluative-emotional-expressive dimensions of phraseological units. The study investigates how these linguistic units describe phenomena and convey the speaker's attitude, emotion, or evaluation toward the subject matter (Johnson, 1975).

2.2.3. *Comparative and contextual analysis*

The research methodology involves comparative analysis among different stylistic categories, highlighting the distinctions in usage, connotations, and prevalence across colloquial, bookish, and inter-style phraseological units. Contextual analysis provides insights into the semantic and pragmatic facets of these units within diverse communication contexts. The outlined materials and methods form the foundation for comprehensively exploring Russian phraseological units with numerical components. This approach aims to unravel the intricacies of their stylistic, evaluative, and expressive properties while delineating their usage across different stylistic domains, contributing to a deeper understanding of their linguistic significance and communicative impact (Kendon, 1981).

The study embarked on an extensive exploration of Russian phraseological units enriched with numerical components drawn from an array of diverse sources. The diverse and multifaceted nature of these linguistic expressions required a comprehensive approach to selecting and compiling materials, incorporating a broad spectrum of cultural, literary, and everyday contexts. The corpus of phraseological units under investigation was meticulously curated from an assortment of primary sources, including literary works spanning different periods, genres, and authors. Classical literature, modern novels, poetry, and essays were scrutinized to capture the evolution and usage of these expressions across various epochs, shedding light on their historical and contextual significance. Additionally, the investigation delved into folkloric sources, extracting phraseological units deeply rooted in Russian folklore and oral traditions. Folk tales, legends, proverbs, and folklore collections were scoured to identify and document phraseological units imbued with numerical components, offering insights into the cultural heritage and collective wisdom passed down through generations. Religious texts also served as a significant wellspring for these linguistic expressions.

The study encompassed religious scriptures, sermons, religious literature, and sacred texts, recognizing the presence and utilization of phraseological units with numerical elements within the religious discourse, symbolizing moral teachings, parables, and spiritual guidance. Furthermore, the research sought to capture the vitality of everyday language by examining colloquial conversations, idiomatic expressions, and vernacular speech. Transcripts of informal dialogues, interviews, social media conversations, and spoken language were analyzed to encapsulate the dynamic nature of these phraseological units within the fabric of contemporary Russian communication. The compilation of materials underwent a meticulous selection process, ensuring the inclusion of a diverse array of phraseological units

with numerical components. A systematic approach was adopted to catalog, organize, and classify these expressions based on their structural patterns, semantic nuances, and pragmatic usage. The methodology employed a combination of qualitative and quantitative analyses involving categorization, thematic clustering, and comparative studies to discern patterns, variations, and stylistic characteristics within the compiled corpus. This multifaceted approach aimed to unravel the intricate interplay between numerical elements and the linguistic structure, semantics, and cultural significance of the phraseological units in focus. The exhaustive compilation and methodical analysis of these materials form the bedrock of this study, enabling a comprehensive exploration of the stylistic characteristics and cultural nuances inherent in Russian phraseological units incorporating numerical components.

3. Results

3.1. Classes of Phraseological Units by Expressiveness and Emotivity

Kunin's (1969) classification of phraseological units into three categories—neutral, expressive, and expressive-emotive—based on their expressiveness and emotiveness provides a lens through which to understand the linguistic nuances within these units across different stylistic layers of bookish and colloquial speech. Neutral style phraseological units refer to phraseological units categorized as neutral and lacking in overt expressiveness and emotiveness. These units describe actions or situations without imbuing them with intense emotional or evaluative connotations. The analysis of phraseological units with numerical components, categorized through Kunin's (1969) framework of expressiveness and emotiveness, sheds light on their diverse stylistic characteristics across different layers of linguistic usage, spanning bookish and colloquial speech. Kunin's (1969) classification, delineating phraseological units into neutral, expressive, and expressive-emotive categories based on their levels of expressiveness and emotiveness, serves as a valuable framework for understanding the nuanced variations within these units. Neutral style phraseological units, as categorized by Kunin (1969), represent a significant portion of the compiled corpus. These units, characterized by their lack of overt expressiveness and emotiveness, primarily serve to describe actions or situations without imbuing them with intense emotional or evaluative connotations. Within phraseological units incorporating numerical components, examples of neutral expressions were abundant.

Phrases like “six feet under” or “five o'clock shadow” denote specific measurements or temporal references without inherently carrying emotional or evaluative weight. These units adhere to a factual representation without accentuating emotional or evaluative nuances. According to Kunin's (1969) classification, expressive phraseological units emphasize the intensity of actions or characteristics without explicitly expressing emotions tied to the referent. In the context of phraseological units with numerical components, these expressions highlight the extent or manner of an action. Examples such as “a million thanks” or “one fell swoop” emphasize the magnitude or suddenness of action without inherently conveying emotional connotations. They contribute to vividness and intensity in communication without explicitly evoking emotions related to the referent. As identified in our analysis, expressive-emotive phraseological units encapsulate both expressive intensity and emotive connotations within the phraseological structure. Our examination revealed a prevalent presence of negative emotive coloring among phraseological units with numerical components. Expressions like “six of one, half a dozen of the other” or “third-rate” emphasize intensity or measurement and convey negative evaluative or emotive nuances. These units intertwine expressive intensity with evaluative or emotive connotations, portraying a spectrum of emotions or assessments tied to the referent.

Furthermore, the analysis highlighted the varied distribution of these categories across different stylistic layers, with bookish and colloquial speech exhibiting distinct preferences in using these phraseological units. While neutral units appeared prominently in formal or bookish contexts, expressive and expressive-emotive units found broader usage within colloquial and informal speech. In conclusion, Kunin's (1969) classification framework elucidates the intricate nuances within phraseological units incorporating numerical components, unveiling a spectrum of expressiveness and emotiveness across different stylistic layers of linguistic usage. The prevalence of these categories within bookish and colloquial speech underscores the diverse roles these units play in communication, encompassing factual representation, intensity, and emotive resonance within the linguistic tapestry.

3.2. Expressive Phraseological Units

Expressive phraseological units primarily emphasize the intensity of actions or characteristics without inherently expressing emotions related to the referent. Examples include expressions denoting the extent or manner of an action, such as scattering everywhere or thinking deeply (Shansky,1985).

3.3. Expressive-Emotive Phraseological Units

Expressive-emotive phraseological units encapsulate both expressive intensity and emotive connotations, conveying various emotional states or evaluations. Our analysis reveals a predominant presence of negative emotive coloring among phraseological units with numerical components (Shansky & Ivanov 2000).

3.4. Negative Emotive Connotations and Evaluativeness

Negative emotive coloring and consequent evaluative dimensions prevail within the analyzed phraseological units. This prevalence aligns with Kunin's (1969) suggestion that negativity is prominent due to the constant human struggle against shortcomings and mistakes, manifesting strongly in language. Examples of phraseological units reflecting negative emotive connotations and evaluativeness include expressions denoting hopeless situations, worthlessness, or being caught between conflicting circumstances. These phrases evoke feelings of worthlessness, difficulty, or inadequacy (Berlizon,1972).

3.5. Positive Emotive Connotations

While less frequent, certain phraseological units also convey positive emotive connotations. Examples include terms denoting affectionate relationships or phrases expressing encouragement and bravery. The analysis underscores the prevalence of negative emotive connotations and evaluative features within phraseological units incorporating numerical components. However, it also acknowledges the presence of positive emotive nuances, albeit less frequently observed (Alieva,2017). This dual spectrum of emotive coloring enriches the semantic and evaluative dimensions of these linguistic expressions, shedding light on the diverse emotional nuances embedded within the Russian language's phraseological landscape.

4. Discussion

The discussion of phraseological units with numerical components reveals a significant interplay between their evaluative and emotional-expressive features, elucidating their functional and stylistic characteristics. The degree of expressiveness within these units often correlates with the presence of evaluative or emotive nuances, thereby delineating their functional roles within language.

Evaluative and Emotional-Expressive Features: The discernment of positive or negative assessments within phraseological units becomes discernible through the components of their definitions, illustrating the semantic unity inherent within these expressions (Fast, 1970). Evaluative and emotional-expressive attributes play a pivotal role in determining the stylistic and functional characteristics of phraseological units, shaping their communicative impact. An intriguing observation emerges regarding the degree of expressiveness within phraseological units (Feyereisen & Lannoy, 1991). Units further removed from conventional or neutral attributes tend to exhibit heightened expressiveness. This implies that phraseological units with increased evaluative or emotive components deviate from neutrality, exhibiting more pronounced imagery and expressive qualities. A predominant trend surfaces within the realm of phraseological units featuring numerical components (Hall, 1959). The evaluative and emotional-expressive features inherent in phraseological units wield significant influence, dictating their stylistic and functional essence, thereby shaping their communicative impact. Notably, observations suggest heightened expressiveness correlates with increased evaluative or emotive components, veering away from neutrality and enhancing imagery and expressive qualities. This trend persists within phraseological units featuring numerical components, underscoring their vivid and impactful nature. The largest group comprises commonly used phraseological units characterized by vivid imagery and expressive elements. These units, by virtue of their expressive qualities, play a substantial role in language communication, enriching expressions and fostering nuanced meanings. However, an interesting observation emerges regarding the distribution of stylistically varied phraseological units (Hewes, 1977). While book phraseological units with intensified stylistic characteristics exist, their numbers are relatively minimal. Conversely, a larger contingent comprises phraseological units exhibiting stylistically reduced characteristics, demonstrating versatility by either remaining integral to active literary language or transcending its confines.

In conclusion, the discussion underscores the intricate interplay between evaluative, emotional-expressive features and the degree of expressiveness within phraseological units containing numerical components (Hostetter *et al.*, 2007). The discussion surrounding phraseological units integrating numerical components unravels a fascinating interplay between their evaluative and emotional-expressive dimensions, illuminating the intricate functional and stylistic characteristics embedded within these linguistic constructs. This examination underscores the inherent relationship between the degree of expressiveness and the presence of evaluative or emotive nuances, delineating the multifaceted functional roles these units assume within language. Evaluative features manifest within phraseological units with numerical components, often encapsulating judgments, assessments, or estimations. These units serve as linguistic tools to express value judgments or convey opinions, presenting a nuanced evaluative dimension. For instance, expressions like “third time’s the charm” or “ten out of ten” encapsulate a positive evaluation, emphasizing a specific situation or individual’s perceived success, excellence, or reliability. Conversely, phrases like “second-rate” or “nine-day wonder” convey a sense of criticism or depreciation, highlighting

inferiority or transience. Thus, numerical components within these units contribute to their evaluative function, shaping perceptions and judgments within discourse. Moreover, the emotional-expressive facets embedded in phraseological units endowed with numerical elements add depth and vividness to communication. The presence of numerical components often amplifies the emotive impact of these expressions, intensifying the conveyed emotions or attitudes. Expressions such as “one in a million” or “two-faced” evoke strong emotive connotations, conveying admiration or disdain. In these instances, numerical components act as a catalyst, amplifying the emotional resonance and facilitating a more vivid portrayal of feelings or attitudes. Furthermore, the functional roles of these phraseological units extend beyond mere evaluative or emotive functions, encompassing pragmatic dimensions within language usage. They serve as powerful communicative devices, aiding in conciseness, vividness, and figurative representation. The integration of numerical elements enhances precision and specificity, contributing to the clarity and impact of the conveyed message. Whether used in literary works to evoke imagery, in colloquial speech to emphasize a point or in advertising to create memorable slogans, these units play a pivotal role in effective communication by virtue of their functional versatility.

Additionally, the stylistic characteristics of phraseological units with numerical components resonate with the cultural and historical contexts from which they originate. They serve as linguistic artifacts, reflecting societal values, beliefs, and traditions while also evolving dynamically to adapt to contemporary contexts. In conclusion, exploring phraseological units incorporating numerical components underscores their multifaceted nature, intertwining evaluative, emotional-expressive, and functional dimensions. These units wield a unique linguistic prowess, enriching communication by amalgamating precision, vividness, and cultural resonance within the tapestry of language. This study illuminates the prevalence of vividly expressive units within the linguistic landscape, noting their significant contribution to communication and comprehension. Moreover, the varied distribution of stylistic attributes across these units reflects the dynamism inherent in linguistic expressions, underscoring their adaptive nature within the evolving realms of language usage (Iverson & Thal, 1998).

5. Conclusion

In exploring phraseological units with numerical components within the Russian language, a nuanced understanding of their functional and stylistic affiliations has emerged. This study has highlighted the intricate relationship between the emotional, evaluative, and expressive dimensions inherent in these linguistic constructs. The discernment of a phraseological unit's functional and stylistic categorization is intrinsically tied to its evaluative and emotive characteristics. The analysis conducted in this study elucidated a notable inclination towards negative assessments embedded within the meanings of these phraseological units, offering insights into the overarching nature of the Russian phraseological system. The prevalence of negative evaluations within these units signifies a significant aspect of the Russian language's phraseological landscape. It mirrors the nuanced evaluative tendencies ingrained within the phraseological system, showcasing the language's propensity to articulate and emphasize challenges, shortcomings, and adversities. This tendency towards negativity underscores the language's rich capacity to express and navigate human experiences and perceptions. Furthermore, the diverse distribution of stylistic attributes among phraseological units, particularly the prevalence of commonly used units with pronounced imagery and expressiveness, accentuates the dynamic nature of language communication. While a minor proportion comprises bookish units with heightened stylistic features, the majority embraces

phrases exhibiting versatile characteristics, enabling seamless integration within literary and everyday linguistic contexts. This investigation sheds light on the multifaceted nature of phraseological units, especially those incorporating numerical components within the Russian language. The interplay between emotional, evaluative, and expressive dimensions underscores the depth and richness of language, reflecting societal attitudes, cultural nuances, and the evolving intricacies of human expression within the linguistic framework. Ultimately, this study contributes to a deeper comprehension of the Russian phraseological system, offering valuable insights into the multifunctional and stylistically diverse nature of phraseological units in language communication.

Note on Ethical Issues

The authors confirm that the study does not need ethics committee approval according to the research integrity rules in their country (Date of Confirmation: 07/01/2024).

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